

DETERMINANTS OF FRAUD IN PROCUREMENT OF GOODS AND SERVICES WITH GENDER AND EXPERIENCE AS MODERATING VARIABLES IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES IN BALI

Gusti Ayu Komang Yanti Yulansari ¹ and I Ketut Sujana ²

^{1,2} Udayana University, Indonesia.

Email: ¹yantiyulan@gmail.com, ²ketutsujana_fe@unud.ac.id

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Abstract

The allocation of funds for procurement of goods/services in private universities is very large, so the opportunity for fraud is very likely to occur. This research aims to analyze aspects of pressure/stimulus (pressure), opportunity (opportunity), rationalization (rationalization), capability, arrogance (arrogance), collusion (collusion) in the fraud hexagon towards fraud in procurement of goods and services as well as to analyze gender and experience as moderating variable on fraud in procurement of goods and services. This research uses a quantitative approach. The sample used was 100 respondents from private universities in Bali. The sampling technique in this research is a purposive sampling technique. Data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques with the help of SmartPLS 4.0 software. The results of this research show that the aspects of pressure/stimulus (pressure), opportunity (opportunity), rationalization (rationalization), capability, arrogance (arrogance), collusion (collusion) in the fraud hexagon have a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services. The results also show that Gender weakens the influence of Hexagon fraud on goods and services procurement fraud and Experience strengthens the influence of Hexagon fraud on goods and services procurement fraud. These findings provide theoretical and practical contributions in minimizing the opportunity for fraud in the procurement of goods and services in private universities in Bali. The results of this research also provide direction for universities to always monitor or carry out regular supervision of their experienced employees by providing coaching and training to all structural employees so that all employees understand more about their operations and duties and can prevent fraud.

Keywords: fraud hexagon, fraudprocurement of goods and services, universities.

INTRODUCTION

Higher education is an academic unit that carries out the educational process. Education has a higher purpose to make the nation's life more intelligent. However, adequate facilities must be supported. Complete facilities are needed to make teaching activities easy. According to Jamil (2012), higher education is a means of producing students who have morals. In order to become a student with morals, universities must be free from existing corrupt practices. Corruption cases that take place in universities are a serious blow to educational institutions in Indonesia. In order for education to be better in the future, educational institutions that are a forum or place for the community to work together in a systematic, orderly and controlled manner must be able to use existing facilities. The ineffectiveness of internal control within higher education institutions can give rise to allegations of corruption cases.

The picture of fraud in higher education is revealed from print media reports and journals. For example, the Australian Broadcasting Corporation reported how Australian university standards were being compromised by acts of fraud. This happened as a result of the university's pressure to recruit foreign students and ensure

they passed the entrance exams, so that they could get the funds they needed. International Education Studies, reveals the case of College Deans in Russia. who accepted a bribe of €30,000 for a PhD claim, and the Moscow Police report that around 30-40 professors in Russia are arrested every year for bribes providing good reviews. In May 2015, South African authorities closed 42 fake colleges and universities offering fake, unaccredited programs and degrees within 15 days. In Nigeria, fraud crimes most often occur among academic staff, especially in promotions, journals, book publications and the exploitation of money for grades (Andri, et al., 2020). Fraud is an important issue that attracts or attracts a lot of media attention, because fraud is an entity that is not easily avoided by companies in the modern world(Ruri and Yasinta, 2024).

Several cases of alleged corruption that have hit higher education institutions in Bali include the Indonesian Arts Institute (ISI) related to corruption in B-Art Grant Funds amounting to 800 million. Udayana University, as the largest state university in Bali, is also not free from allegations of corruption in the procurement of medical equipment for the Special Hospital for Teaching Infectious Diseases and Tourism in 2009. In the far north, Ganesha Education University is indicated to have marked up land prices in procuring land for the campus. One of the private universities was also identified as a suspected corruption case, namely the Indonesian Hindu University (UNHI), owned by PHDI, which was also reported to the authorities regarding non-transparent fund management.(Mahaputra, 2017). The Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) announced that fraud in the procurement of goods and services still often occurs in universities. Apart from that, the Corruption Eradication Commission also found fraud in the procurement of goods and services at state universities in Indonesia. This indication shows that it is very easy for employees who handle the procurement of new goods and services to manipulate, resulting in quite large state losses.

Corruption as a form of fraud that occurs in higher education is caused by the ineffectiveness of existing fraud control. In controlling fraudulent practices in higher education, it is necessary to improve the control system for goods and services, to provide protection against fraud designed to prevent irregularities and efforts to detect fraud early (Silverstone, and Sheetz, 2007). Fraud in the procurement of goods and services is fraudulent behavior that is planned to influence every step of the procurement flow in order to gain financial profit or result in loss(Nuora and Ana, 2015). The fraud hexagon theory according to Vousinas (2019), states that there are 6 (six) elements behind a person committing fraud, namely pressure, opportunity, rationalization, competence, arrogance), and collusion. The use of the fraud hexagon theory in goods and services fraud includes: stimulus is the first element in the fraud hexagon. Vousinas explained that when management is facing financial or non-financial pressure, a stimulus will occur (Vousinas, 2019).

Opportunities can trigger fraud in financial reports. Opportunity is a circumstance or setting that allows managers to commit fraud for financial gain (Sari & Herawaty, 2022). Capability is an element of the fraud hexagon which explains the employee's knowledge in company development and the ability to influence social conditions that may benefit him, known as capability (Desviana et al., 2020). Collusion is the final element in the fraud hexagon. Collusion can lead to crimes and acts of fraud by collaborating between several individuals to achieve the main goal, namely acts of fraud (Vousinas, 2019). False financial reporting is not influenced by inadequate oversight, changes in auditors or directors, selfishness, or collaboration (Achmad, et al., 2022). Melati in Karmila and Parinduri's research stated that inadequate capacity, monitoring and rationalization had a major impact on financial reporting control (Kamila & Parinduri, 2023).

According to Ardianingsih (2018), previous research on fraud in higher education shows that finances, bad habits, work environment, and others result in the emergence of pressure (Vousinas, 2019). The research results of Agustina and Pratomo (2019) state that partial pressure shows a significant negative influence on fraud (Agustina & Pratomo, 2019). Fitri and Nadirsyah's (2019) research states that rationalization has no effect on fraud. The rationale that justifies one's behavior as a normal action, which is ethically acceptable to the public is called rationalization. Fraudulent individuals often try to find reasons to justify their actions (Fitri & Nadirsyah, 2019). Wijayanto's research (2020) explains that competence has a positive effect on fraud. On research (Rahmida & Urumsah, 2020), gender is not proven to be a variable that can moderate the relationship between pentagon fraud and control of fraud in procurement of goods and services. This may be because men and women in carrying out fraud control efforts have the same competence in processing existing information or data.

The choice of private universities as the research population is due to the different regulatory policies for the procurement of goods and services between private universities, although they still use the SPI guidelines in the Ministerial Regulation of the Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education of the Republic of Indonesia No. 19 of 2015. Apart from that, logically, the allocation of funds The procurement of goods/services in private universities is very large, so the opportunity for fraud is very likely to occur. Therefore, it is necessary to control funds well in improving the quality of private universities, although in practice it is often not optimal, therefore it is important to carry out research to analyze the factors that motivate the occurrence of fraud so that the results of the research can later provide regulatory formulations in controlling and preventing fraud crimes, especially in procurement of goods at private universities.

Formulation of the problem

Based on the explanation of the background above, the problem in this research is formulated as follows:

1. Does the pressure/stimulus (pressure) aspect in the fraud hexagon have an effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services?
2. Does the opportunity aspect in the fraud hexagon affect fraud in the procurement of goods and services?
3. Does the rationalization aspect in the fraud hexagon affect fraud in the procurement of goods and services?
4. Does the capability aspect in the fraud hexagon affect fraud in procurement of goods and services?
5. Does the aspect of arrogance/Ego (arrogance) in the fraud hexagon have an effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services?
6. Does the collusion aspect in the fraud hexagon affect fraud in the procurement of goods and services?
7. Do gender and experience as moderating variables of the Fraud Hexagon have an effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Procurement

In terms of the producer-supplier-consumer flow, procurement or procurement of goods and services is attached to the design of business principles that involve various parties. Then, in the planning and management aspect, procurement of goods and services is also based on management planning (Malik, 2017). The business process described by Kotler et al., (2005) includes all things related to the series of goods and services procurement flows, starting with the entrepreneur's efforts to fulfill what consumers ask for, the production process, the process of introducing goods and building consumer awareness (brand awareness).

Fraud Procurement of Goods (Procurement Fraud)

Planned fraudulent behavior which is defined as influencing every step of the procurement flow in order to gain financial profit or result in loss, is usually called goods and services procurement fraud. This step can be carried out by contractors outside the organization, as well as staff within the organization (Authority, 2011). In the procurement of goods and services, acts of fraud that are often encountered are discrepancies between the goods and services agreed upon in the agreement for organizational needs, both in terms of form, quality and quantity.

METHODS

Framework of thinking

The thinking framework is prepared based on a literature review and relevant or related research findings. A good theoretical structure of thinking describes the relationship between the variables studied. This theoretical framework analysis model was developed based on a review of available literature. This can be seen from the presentation of the theoretical framework and hypotheses presented in this section.

Research Concept

This research includes descriptive research with a quantitative approach using survey methods to analyze the relationship between the fraud hexagon as an independent variable and efforts to control procurement fraud as a dependent variable in private universities in Bali.

Figure 1. Research Concept

Data Types and Sources

The type of data used in this research is quantitative data. Quantitative data is data that can be measured or calculated directly, in the form of information or explanations expressed in numbers or in the form of numbers. The data source used in this research is a primary data source, where the primary data source is obtained directly from the original source in the form of responses.

Method of collecting data

The data collection method used in this research is a survey method with a questionnaire. Questionnaires can be distributed directly or via email by researchers who are then forwarded to each respondent at a private university in Bali.

Data Analysis Techniques

Obtaining related information contained in the data and using the results to find solutions to research problems can be carried out using data analysis (Ghozali, and Laten, 2015). There are two ways to analyze the data in this research, namely

descriptive analysis and quantitative analysis. To analyze the descriptions of respondents and variables, descriptive analysis was used, while to find out the relationship between the variables used in this research, quantitative analysis was used. In carrying out this data analysis technique the author uses the help of Smart-PLS software.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out using the bootstrap resampling method developed by Geisser and Stone (1975). The test statistic used is the t statistic or t test. The application of the resampling method allows for distribution free data, does not require normal distribution assumptions, and does not require a large sample (a minimum sample of 30 is recommended). Testing is carried out using a t-test, if the t-count > t-table and p-value < 0.05 is obtained, it is concluded that the hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION

Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

To analyze the research model, the Partial Least Square (PLS) method was used with the SmartPLS 4.0 program tool. There are two basic model evaluations in this test, namely the outer model and the inner model.

Convergent validity

Convergent validity with reflexive indicators it can be seen from the correlation between scores indicator with variable scores.

Table 1. Outer Loading Test Results

	X1.	X2.	X3.	X4.	X5.	X6.	Y
X1.1	0.891						
X1.2	0.922						
X1.3	0.855						
X1.4	0.822						
X2.1		0.820					
X2.2		0.888					
X2.3		0.944					
X2.4		0.873					

	X1.	X2.	X3.	X4.	X5.	X6.	Y
X3.1			0.869				
X3.2			0.891				
X3.3			0.916				
X3.4			0.944				
X3.5			0.907				
X4.1				0.882			
X4.2				0.918			
X4.3				0.906			
X4.4				0.868			
X5.1					0.915		
X5.2					0.894		
X5.3					0.922		
X5.4					0.912		
X6.1						0.938	
X6.2						0.923	
X6.3						0.912	
Y1							0.768
Y2							0.834
Y3							0.918
Y4							0.877
Y5							0.855
Y6							0.924
Y7							0.850

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

The results of the convergent validity test in Table 4.1 show that all outer loading values of variable indicators have values greater than 0.70. Thus, it can be concluded that all indicators have met the convergent validity requirements.

Figure 2. PLS Algorithm Test Results

Fornell-larcker criterion

In the next stage, an evaluation is carried out through discriminant validity, namely looking at the Fornell-Larcker criterion value which states that each construct must have a squared AVE value greater than the correlation value between other constructs.

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker Calculation Results

	X1.	X2.	X3.	X4.	X5.	X6.	Y
X1.	0.873						
X2.	0.624	0.882					
X3.	0.679	0.800	0.906				
X4.	0.711	0.644	0.879	0.894			
X5.	0.585	0.722	0.815	0.788	0.911		
X6.	0.562	0.656	0.743	0.687	0.747	0.924	

Y	0.716	0.806	0.832	0.802	0.844	0.783	0.862
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Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

The table shows that the indicators for each variable have a squared AVE value that is greater than the correlation value of a construct below it. For example, it can be seen in the variable Based on table 5.12, it can be explained that the Fornell-Larcker value for all constructs has a value of >0.50, meaning that all variables have met the feasibility of the Fornell-Larcker evaluation model.

Cross Loading

Cross loading is the correlation value between the indicator and the variable being measured.

Table 3. Cross Loading Calculation Results

	X1.	X2.	X3.	X4.	X5.	X6.	Y
X1.1	0.891	0.511	0.555	0.603	0.473	0.486	0.614
X1.2	0.922	0.585	0.663	0.668	0.591	0.563	0.682
X1.3	0.855	0.448	0.508	0.549	0.432	0.470	0.528
X1.4	0.822	0.616	0.626	0.649	0.525	0.437	0.656
X2.1	0.497	0.820	0.688	0.666	0.661	0.599	0.784
X2.2	0.566	0.888	0.774	0.757	0.552	0.472	0.765
X2.3	0.584	0.944	0.863	0.801	0.691	0.647	0.852
X2.4	0.554	0.873	0.845	0.750	0.638	0.589	0.793
X3.1	0.550	0.841	0.869	0.760	0.646	0.568	0.809
X3.2	0.656	0.860	0.891	0.796	0.737	0.685	0.871
X3.3	0.661	0.774	0.916	0.789	0.776	0.688	0.851
X3.4	0.608	0.829	0.944	0.808	0.751	0.694	0.861
X3.5	0.596	0.770	0.907	0.829	0.776	0.726	0.824
X4.1	0.663	0.819	0.730	0.882	0.592	0.488	0.783
X4.2	0.653	0.788	0.791	0.918	0.690	0.593	0.811

	X1.	X2.	X3.	X4.	X5.	X6.	Y
X4.3	0.654	0.728	0.849	0.906	0.789	0.677	0.847
X4.4	0.570	0.682	0.768	0.868	0.741	0.695	0.780
X5.1	0.549	0.733	0.816	0.768	0.915	0.677	0.802
X5.2	0.487	0.568	0.669	0.681	0.894	0.693	0.698
X5.3	0.578	0.667	0.765	0.736	0.922	0.707	0.803
X5.4	0.508	0.652	0.708	0.682	0.912	0.647	0.765
X6.1	0.554	0.655	0.717	0.649	0.669	0.938	0.741
X6.2	0.512	0.622	0.697	0.665	0.734	0.923	0.757
X6.3	0.488	0.534	0.642	0.587	0.665	0.912	0.667
Y1	0.469	0.736	0.657	0.656	0.558	0.526	0.768
Y2	0.657	0.782	0.746	0.801	0.620	0.505	0.834
Y3	0.667	0.889	0.849	0.832	0.743	0.708	0.918
Y4	0.621	0.854	0.853	0.743	0.742	0.682	0.877
Y5	0.624	0.715	0.809	0.750	0.783	0.721	0.855
Y6	0.675	0.809	0.882	0.828	0.814	0.785	0.924
Y7	0.590	0.677	0.806	0.821	0.812	0.771	0.850

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

Average Variance Extracted(AVE)

Another discriminant validity test is by assessing the validity of the variable from the average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Table 4. Calculation Results Average Variance Extracted(AVE)

Variable	Average variance extracted (AVE)
X1.	0.763

Variable	Average variance extracted (AVE)
X2.	0.778
X3.	0.820
X4.	0.799
X5.	0.829
X6.	0.854
Y	0.743

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

Table 4.4 above shows that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value in this study has the result that each indicator value is above 0.5. Thus the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value meets the criteria. The results of all validity tests in the outer model by assessing convergent validity, discriminant validity and AVE values show that all indicators are valid.

Composite reliability

Besides testing validity, a reliability test of variables was also carried out which was measured using two criteria, namely composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha from the indicator block that measured the variables.

Table 5 Results of Instrument Reliability Research

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Criteria
X1.	0.896	0.903	0.928	Reliable
X2.	0.904	0.907	0.933	Reliable
X3.	0.945	0.946	0.958	Reliable
X4.	0.916	0.917	0.941	Reliable
X5.	0.931	0.934	0.951	Reliable
X6.	0.915	0.918	0.946	Reliable
Y	0.942	0.946	0.953	Reliable

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

Results *output composite reliability* and Cronbach's alpha variables Pressure (X1), Opportunity (X2), Rationalization (X3), Competence (X4), Ego (Arrogance) (X5), Collusion (X6) and fraud in procurement of goods and services (Y) are all above 0.70. Thus, it can be explained that all variables have good reliability.

Inner Model Evaluation Test Results

After the data has passed the outer model test, data processing for the research variables can be continued at the structural model testing stage to be able to fulfill the contribution of the independent variables (X) to the dependent variables (Y).

Table 6 Goodness of Fit Test Results

Variable	R Square	Average variance extracted (AVE)
X1.		0.763
X2.		0.778
X3.		0.820
X4.		0.799
X5.		0.829
X6.		0.854
Y	0.945	0.743
Average	0.945	0.798

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

Based on the results of the Goodness of Fit (GoF) calculation above, a GoF value of 0.868 was obtained, so it can be concluded that the model that can be used in this research has a relatively large suitability for the research model (Hair, 2017).

R-Square (R2) and Q Square (Q2) Test Results

The R-Square value is used to measure the level of variation in changes in the independent variable towards the dependent variable.

Table 7. Results Coefficient of Determination R-Square (R2)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted

Y (Fraud in procurement of goods and services)	0.945	0.939
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Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

Regarding fraud in the procurement of goods and services, it gives an R-square value of 0.945, which can be interpreted that the variability of the fraud variable in the procurement of goods and services can be explained by the variability of the variables Pressure (X1), Opportunity (X2), Rationalization (X3), Competence (X4), Ego. (X5), Collusion (X6), Gender, Experience, interaction variables *fraud Hexagon(X)* with gender (XG) and interaction variables *fraud Hexagon(X)* with experience (XP) amounted to 94.5 percent, while 5.5 percent was explained by other variables outside those studied.

Table 8. Q Square Test Results

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1- SSE/SSO)
Y (Fraud in procurement of goods and services)	700,000	221,599	0.683

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 12)

The Q2 value has a value in the range $0 < Q2 < 1$, where the closer to 1 means the model is better. The results of these calculations show that the Q2 value is 0.683, so it can be concluded that the model has good predictive relevance.

Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis testing uses path analysis using SEM Smart PLS. Path analysis shows the direct and indirect effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable with the mediating variable.

The results of the research bootstrapping analysis using Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis can be seen in Figure 5.2 as follows.

Figure 4. Empirical Research Model

Table 9. Hypothesis Testing Results (Path Coefficients)

Hypothesis	Connection Between Variables	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Conclusion
H1	X1. -> Y	0.111	2,801	0.005	Significant Positive
H2	X2. -> Y	0.263	3,263	0.001	Significant Positive
H3	X3. -> Y	0.265	2,211	0.027	Significant Positive
H4	X4. -> Y	0.179	2,650	0.008	Significant Positive
H5	X5. -> Y	0.157	2,289	0.022	Significant Positive

H6	X6. -> Y	0.137	2,364	0.018	Significant Positive
H7a	Gender -> Y	0.219	2,394	0.017	Able to Moderate
	XG -> Y	-0.212	2,013	0.044	
H7b	Experience -> Y	-0.294	2,538	0.011	Able to Moderate
	XP -> Y	0.250	2,081	0.037	

Source: Data Processed Results, 2024 (Appendix 13)

1. The t statistics value was obtained at 2.801 (> t-critical 1.96) with a p value of 0.005 <0.05, then the influence of pressure on fraud in procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted, namely pressure has a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services.
2. The t statistics value is 3.263 (> t-critical 1.96) with a p value of 0.001<0.05, then the influence of Opportunity on fraud in procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 2 (H2) is accepted, namely opportunity.has a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services..
3. The t statistics value is 2.211 (> t-critical 1.96) with a p value of 0.027 <0.05, then the influence of Rationalization on fraud in procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted, namely rationalization.has a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services.
4. The t statistics value is 2.650 (> t-critical 1.96) with p value 0.008<0.05, then the effectabilityagainst fraud in procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 4 (H4) is accepted, namelyabilityhas a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services.
5. The t statistics value is 2.289 (> t-critical 1.96) with p value 0.022<0.05, then the effectego (arrogance)to*fraud*procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 5 (H5) is accepted, namelyego (arrogance)has a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services.
6. The t statistics value is 2.289 (> t-critical 1.96) with p value 0.022<0.05, then the effectcollusionto*fraud*procurement of goods and services is significant. Thus, hypothesis 6 (H6) is accepted, namelycollusionhas a positive effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services.

Table 10 Classification of Moderating Variables

No.	Moderation Type	Coefficient
1.	<i>PureModeration</i>	b7,8 non-significant b9,10 significant

2.	<i>QuasiModeration</i>	b7.8 significant b9,10 significant
3.	<i>HomologizerModeration</i>	b7.8 non-significant b9,10 non-significant
4.	<i>PredictorsModeration</i>	b7.8 significant b9,10 non-significant

Source: Solimun (2010:34)

The results of the moderation regression analysis show that the regression coefficient value *fraud Hexagon* (β_1) is significantly positive and the regression coefficient value of the interaction variable *fraud Hexagon* against fraud in the procurement of goods and services.

The results of the moderation regression analysis show that the regression coefficient value *fraud Hexagon* (β_1) is positive and the regression coefficient value of the interaction variable XP (β_9) is positive, indicating that there is a unidirectional relationship, so it can be concluded that the experience variable is a moderating variable that strengthens the influence *fraud Hexagon* against fraud in the procurement of goods and services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Pressure has a positive effect on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so the first hypothesis is accepted.
2. Chance has a positive effect on procurement fraud in the procurement of goods and services, so the second hypothesis is accepted.
3. Rationalization has a positive and significant effect on fraud in the procurement of goods and services, so that the third hypothesis is accepted.
4. Ability has a positive effect on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so the fourth hypothesis is accepted.
5. Ego has a positive effect on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so the fifth hypothesis is accepted.
6. Kolusion has a positive effect on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so the sixth hypothesis is accepted.

The results of the PLS test analysis with moderation show that gender weakens the influence *fraud Hexagon* on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so that hypothesis H7a is accepted. This finding means that the higher *fraud Hexagon* those

held by structural employees at private universities in Bali can be weakened by gender moderation, thereby reducing the occurrence of fraud in the procurement of goods and services. The results of the PLS test analysis with moderation also show that experience strengthens the influence *fraud Hexagon* on fraud in procurement of goods and services, so that hypothesis H7b is accepted.

References

- 1) Achmad, T., Ghozali, I., & Pamungkas, I. D. (2022). Hexagon Fraud: Detection of Fraudulent Financial Reporting in State-Owned Enterprises Indonesia. *Economies*, 10(1), 13.
- 2) Agustina, R. D., & Pratomo, D. (2019). Pengaruh Fraud Pentagon Dalam Mendeteksi Kecurangan Pelaporan Keuangan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, & Akuntansi(MEA)*, 3(1), 44–62.
- 3) Andri Astuti Itasari, Nurnawati Hindra Hastuti, A. S. (2020). Pengaruh Word of Mouth, Electronic Word of Mouth dan Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan, *ETTISAL: Journal of Communication*, Vol. 5, No.2, December 2020.
- 4) Authority, N. F. (2011). Procurement Fraud in the Public Sector. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/118460/procurement-fraud-public-sector.pdf.
- 5) Desviana, D., Basri, Y. M., & Nasrizal, N. (2020). Analisis Kecurangan pada Pengelolaan Dana Desa dalam Perspektif Fraud Hexagon. *Studi Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Indonesia*, 3(1), 50–73. <https://doi.org/10.21632/saki.3.1.50-73>
- 6) Ghozali, Imam, H. L. (2015). Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris. BP Undip.
- 7) Jamil, A. (2012). Effects of motivation and parental influence on the educational attainments of students at secondary level. *Academic Research International*, 2(3), 427–431.
- 8) Kamila, F. T., & Parinduri, A. Z. (2023). Pengaruh Fraud Hexagon Terhadap Fraudulent Financial Reporting Dengan Komite Audit Sebagai Variabel Moderasi. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti* <https://www.e-journal.trisakti.ac.id/index.php/jet> Vol. 3 No. 1 April 2023 : Hal : 1407-1416 <http://dx.doi.org/10.25105/jet.v3i1.16090> e-ISSN 2339-0840, 12(2), 196–213.
- 9) Mahaputra, L. K. M. dan I. N. K. A. (2017). Moralitas, Pengendalian Internal dan Gender Dalam kecenderungan Terjadinya Fraud. *Jurnal Akuntansi/Volume XXI*, No. 01, Januari 2017: 35-46.
- 10) Malik, A. A. (2017). Teori Pengadaan Barang Dan Jasa Publik teori Pengadaan Barang Dan Jasa Publik. *Universitas Bakrie*, September 2017, 1–43., 2(2), 415–425.
- 11) Nuora Ayuning Kusuma, Ana Irhandayaningsih, A. T. K. (2015). Analisis Penggunaan Metode Mind Mapping Untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca Pemahaman (Studi Kualitatif Siswa Tunarungu SD Kelas V di SLB Negeri Semarang. *Jurnal Ilmu Perpustakaan* Vol. 4, No. 2 (2015): April 2015, 1(1), 96–104.
- 12) Silverstone, H. and Sheetz, M. (2007) *Forensic Accounting and Fraud. Investigation for Non-Experts*. 2nd Edition. New Jersey USA: John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- 13) Vousinas, G. L. (2019). Implementasi Kebijakan Ketahanan Pangan dan Gizi di Kabupaten Subang.